

METHODOLOGY FOR USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES WHEN TEACHING RUSSIAN TO FOREIGN STUDENTS

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Annotation

This article discusses some methods of using innovative technologies in the process of teaching Russian to foreign students. The relevance of innovative teaching lies in the use of person-centered learning, as well as in the search for conditions for unleashing the student's creative potential, which is the main requirement of modern education.

Keywords: modern education, improve yourself ,innovative teaching, student-centered learning , artistic reading .

Modern education is interested in teachers mastering the use of modern educational technologies in their lessons. The use of innovative technologies by teachers in the classroom when teaching children from foreign backgrounds the Russian language is becoming an objective necessity. Today there should not be a teacher who would not think about the questions: "How to make the lesson interesting and meaningful? How to interest children in your subject? How to create a situation of creative success for each student in the classroom?"

The main goal of education at the present stage is not only the accumulation by the student of a certain amount of knowledge, skills, abilities, but also the preparation of the student as an independent subject of educational activity. The basis of modern education is the activity of the student, directed by the teacher. It is precisely this goal - the education of a creative, active personality who can learn, think critically, and improve independently - that is the main goal of modern education.

The development of intellectual, communicative, linguistic and creative abilities of students, the formation of personal qualities of students, the development of skills that influence educational and cognitive activity, the formation of key competencies of students and the transition to the level of productive creativity are the main goals of innovative teaching.

In teaching activities, it is advisable to use project activities. Project activities are based on collective, group or individual work to solve practical

problems. Solving them requires possession of a large amount of knowledge and certain skills: - intellectual (the ability to work with information and text, search for and analyze it, draw conclusions); - communicative (the ability to conduct a discussion, dialogue, defend one's opinion); - creative (the ability to predict the consequences of a particular phenomenon, the ability to carry out generalized mental actions in variable conditions for solving educational problems). When using project technology, students independently study and analyze various sources of information on the topic; work with dictionaries; with Internet resources; collect and summarize the necessary information; demonstrate the results obtained. Project-based learning creates positive motivation for self-education. Students see real-world applications of their knowledge. They develop a sense of responsibility to their comrades for part of their work. When preparing to defend their project, the guys structure their presentation so that it is reasoned, clear and logical, which develops, in addition to logic and thinking, a culture of speech. Experience has shown that working on a project makes it possible for even weak and often passive students to express themselves in the learning process, and contributes to the development of creativity.

Let's consider those resources that can most often be used in Russian language and literature lessons.

At the present stage of schooling, presentations are most often used. They can be used when explaining new material, consolidating knowledge, and performing creative tasks and physical education lessons. You can insert everything possible into the presentation: drawings, diagrams, tests, and videos. Compared to other resources, the presentation can be considered the most universal, since the use of different types of presentations allows you to solve the following problems:

1. Lecture presentation is a visualization of educational material, with the help of which the content of lectures, reports, speeches of a teacher or students is illustrated.

2. Presentations - "Posters" are a demonstration of illustrations, photographs with a minimum of captions, allow for the active use of animation: field trips to houses-museums of writers, to museum cities, rotating photographs telling about the life and work of writers, etc. create the maximum effect of presence. This type of work awakens a special interest in the study of the Russian language and literature, increases the cognitive activity of foreign students, presentations prepared by the student's work make it possible to affirm his personal self-esteem.

3. The teacher can use animations and illustrations when explaining new material: these resources clearly demonstrate educational material and allow you to observe various language phenomena. These resources can also be used to organize creative work (make a story based on a picture).

The use of cartoons and animation helps to diversify lessons and activates students. A lecture using a multimedia projector sounds interesting in a lesson, when the lecture is accompanied by a demonstration of colorful diagrams to students, various sounds and animations, and quick links to previously studied material are used for explanation.

References:

1. Belskikh, M. A. Application of innovative technologies in Russian language lessons in the conditions of a modern educational school / M. A. Belskikh. — Text: direct // Innovative pedagogical technologies: materials of the V International. scientific conf. (Kazan, October 2016). - Kazan: Buk, 2016. - pp. 50-52. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/conf/ped/archive/207/11129/>
2. Mirzayunusova, Z. I. (2022). Organization of Extracurricular Activities in the Conditions of Russian as a Foreign Language. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(11), 283-289.
3. Мирзаянусова, З. И., & Хосиятхон, М. К. В. (2023). ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 4(KSPI Conference 1), 142-144.
4. Кахарова, Н. (2019). Актуальность использования интерактивных и дидактических методов на занятиях по русскому языку в общеобразовательных учреждениях. in *Library*, 19(2), 4-8.
5. Кахарова, Н. Н. (2023). Дидактический материал как средство повышения познавательной деятельности учащихся на уроках русского языка. In *Фундаментальные и прикладные научные исследования: актуальные вопросы, достижения и инновации* (pp. 170-172).
6. Кахарова, Н. Н. (2022). Роль информационно-образовательных технологий в обучении русскому языку в неязыковой аудитории. In *НАУКА, ОБЩЕСТВО, ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ И ГЛОБАЛЬНЫХ ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ* (pp. 128-131).
7. Половина, Л. В. (2023). МЕТОДЫ И ПРИЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ СКЛОНЕНИЯ ИМЕН СУЩЕСТВИТЕЛЬНЫХ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 5(NUU Conference 2), 512-517.

8. Половина, Л. (2023). Изучение русского языка как иностранного при помощи игр. Традиции и инновации в исследовании и преподавании языков, 1(1), 493-497.
9. Ботиров, А. А. (2023). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 41, 222-225.